

DESIGN OF LOW POWER OPERATIONAL TRANSCONDUCTANCE AMPLIFIER FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design of folded cascode operational transconductance amplifier (OTA). This design has been implemented in 0.18 μ m CMOS Technology using Cadence. Spectre simulation shows that the OTA has flat gain of 47dB from 1Hz to 100 KHz frequency, indicating stability of OTA, noise ranges as 22.49769nV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 10Hz to 66.89128fV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 1MHz and average power as 0.770mW. In this paper, we will be studying the design concepts, analysis of operational transconductance amplifier which is used for recording the bio signals. This paper plays a key role in real time applications for equipment designing of ECG, EEG, EMG, ENG devices. It is also used in recording and also for treatment of Paralysis, Epilepsy, Neuro diseases etc.,

KEYWORDS

Folded cascode, Operational Transconductance amplifier (OTA), Cadence.

1. INTRODUCTION

By the advancement in Biomedical engineering and neuroscience it became easy to extract control signals from individual and communicate their intentions through computers or prostheses. Thus bio signals can be interfaced to neural interface microsystems and monitor a large group of neurons. But the channel faced by such microsystem is low power constraints, small form factor while providing high resolution.

In such systems Operational Transconductance amplifier plays a very role. They are the main building blocks of analog design but the problem is they consume more power. Basically OTA is an Operational amplifier (op amp) without any buffer. OTA is voltage controlled current source(VCCS) while op amp is voltage controlled voltage source(VCVS).OTA has a differential amplifier at the input. The main purpose of OTA is it provides current proportional to an input voltage difference. The main parameter of OTA is Transconductance i.e., the ratio of output current to input voltage. A simple first-order small signal model for an OTA is shown in Fig. 5.1. The amplifier's transconductance is G_{ma} and its frequency response in Fig. 5.1is given simply by $G_{ma}Z_L$. More over they are widely used because of simple design.

Figure 1. First-order model of an operational transconductance amplifier (OTA) driving a capacitive load.

There are many types of OTAs among which conventional OTAs are: Two stage OTA, folded cascode OTA, Telescopic OTA, Gain Boosted OTA and other OTAs are miller OTA, Current mirror OTA and so on. In this paper a folded cascode OTA is designed to satisfy flat gain and low power.

2. CIRCUIT IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 Design of Folded cascode Operational Transconductance amplifier

In this design we have used differential-input single-ended output folded cascode design. We have used here current mirrors that provide wide swing current mirrors and they are used as they provide High output impedance maximizing the DC gain Of OTA.

The basic idea of folded cascode OTA is to apply cascode transistors to the input differential pair but the transistors used are of opposite type to that of input. In our design we have used differential transistors Q_1 and Q_2 as n-channel transistors and cascode transistors Q_5 and Q_6 as p-channel. This opposite type of transistors provide single gain stage amplifier same Bias voltage at output as that of input signals. Even though the folded cascode is single stage amplifier it has high gain. This high gain is due to the product of input Transconductance and output impedance. The high output impedance is due to cascode techniques used. The shown differential-to-single-ended conversion is realized by the wide-swing current mirror composed of Q_7 , Q_8 , Q_9 , and Q_{10} .

An important addition of the folded-cascode OTA used is the inclusion of two extra transistors, Q_{12} and Q_{13} . They serve two purposes. One is to increase the slew-rate performance of the OTA. During times of slew-rate limiting, these transistors prevent the drain voltages of Q_1 and Q_2 from having large transients where they change from their small-signal voltages to voltages very close to the negative power-supply voltage. Thus the inclusion of Q_{12} and Q_{13} allows the OTA to recover more quickly following a slew-rate condition.

The main purpose of the diode-connected transistors, Q_{12} and Q_{13} included is to clamp the drain voltages of Q_1 or Q_2 so they don't change as much during slew-rate limiting. A second, more subtle effect dynamically increases the bias currents of both Q_3 and Q_4 during times of slew-rate limiting. This increased bias current results in a larger maximum current available for charging or discharging the load capacitance.

Here compensation is provide by the load capacitor C_L , and realizes dominant-pole compensation. In applications where the load capacitance is very small, it is necessary to add additional compensation capacitance in parallel with the load to guarantee stability. If lead compensation is desired, a resistor can be placed in series with C_L .

$$\omega_t = \frac{g_{m1}}{C_L} \quad (4)$$

With feedback, the loop unity-gain frequency is

$$\omega_t = \frac{\beta g_{m1}}{C_L} \quad (5)$$

Hence, for large load capacitances, maximizing the transconductance of the input transistors maximizes the bandwidth. One more advantage of having very large transconductance for the input devices is that the thermal noise due to this input pair is reduced. since much of the bias current in folded-cascode opamps flows through the input differential pair, these opamps often have a better thermal noise performance than other opamp designs having the same power dissipation.

Table 1. Transistors aspect ratios in (μm)

MOSFETS	Practical values(W/L)
NM0(Q1)	40/1.6
NM5(Q2)	40/1.6
PM2(Q3)	40/1.6
PM1(Q4)	40/1.6
PM4(Q5)	30/1.6
PM3(Q6)	30/1.6
NM1(Q7)	15/1.6
NM2(Q8)	15/1.6
NM4(Q9)	15/1.6
NM3(Q10)	15/1.6
PM0(Q11)	10/1.6
NM7(Q12)	40/1.6
NM6(Q13)	10/1.6

3.Simulation results

A folded cascode operational transconductance amplifier is designed with the design process described above and implemented in 0.18 μm process with 1.8 V power supply and simulated with Cadence spectre .The load capacitance is 1 pF. The parameters obtained are:

Figure 3. Folded cascode OTA schematic in cadence.

Figure 4.Symbol for Folded cascode OTA schematic.

Figure 5.Gain of Folded cascode OTA.

Figure 7. Noise Response of Folded cascode OTA.

Figure 9. Average power of Folded cascode OTA.

Table 2. Simulation results

PARAMETER	RESULT
Technology	180nm
C_L	1pF
Noise	22.49769nV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 10Hz 2.890398nV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 100Hz 1.10534nV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 300Hz 51.29049pV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 10KHz 6.25439pV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 100KHz 66.89128fV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 1MHz
Flat gain	≈ 47 dB from 1Hz to 100KHz
Supply Voltage	1.8V

4. Conclusion

The design and experimental results of folded cascode OTA has been presented, based on 0.18 μ m CMOS process, it has good performance with a flat gain of 47 dB approximately from 1Hz to 100KHz, noise ranges as 22.49769nV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 10Hz to 66.89128fV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 1MHz and average power of 0.770mW at a power supply of 1.8 V.

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